

PLAYING AS AN ACTIVE METHODOLOGY IN EARLY EARLY EDUCATION AND IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION I

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13382062

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the importance of the act of playing and in an attempt to make some surveys and foundations to understand its importance for the integral development of Man. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it proposes a debate to re-signify the concept of play beyond what is known, that is, to understand it as an active methodology and not as simple entertainment. Its social relevance lies in presenting to parents and teachers, responsible for the formation of the new generations, the act of playing as an active methodology of paramount importance for the cognitive and socio-emotional development of the individual, as it allows the awakening of the child's interest and willingness to participate in the entire teaching-learning process. It promotes learning. For this, it was used bibliographic research and deductive, inductive, analytical and synthesis methods.

Keywords: Cognitive development. Intelligence. Play, Toys and Inventiveness and technology. Play as an active methodology.

INTRODUCTION

When a *child* expresses himself, in an attempt to be heard, the listener, for a moment, may feel enveloped in nostalgia, as he may be induced to remember the toys and games that are present at this stage of life. Most of the time, this playing involved songs, games, and role-plays

that helped him not only have fun but also understand that, in a game, you can win or lose, learn to respect the other person's turn, and work as a team. , in addition to developing your attention and concentration. Playing, therefore, is fundamental for the intellectual and physical development of the human individual.

Thus, although human beings can boast of all the technological advances and achievements made to date, they are still born small, fragile and dependent on others; and this is characterized as part of the phylogenetic process. This other is usually a family member or a guardian designated for this purpose, that is, he is the one who takes care of, who must ensure that this care helps him, as a child and adolescent, to grow in all aspects, physical, emotional and spiritual. And when that doesn't happen, the State needs to take action. To this end, article 71 of Law No. 8,069 of July 13 , 1990, which provides for the Statute of Children and Adolescents, determines that “children and adolescents have the right to information, culture, leisure, sports, entertainment, shows and products and services that respect their peculiar condition as a developing person” (BRASIL, 1990, sp). Because, due to many factors, among them the adult's negligence in relation to care, not only basic, but also intellectual related to the child and his well-being, even though the law determines that he is guaranteed, mainly, the right to leisure, this has not been fulfilled and we are witnessing the emergence of citizens who are increasingly individualistic, self-centered, perverse and, with an even more pronounced inability to discern what is right and wrong.

To make matters even worse, families, which are the first social group, are forgetting to play with their children and are allowing them to consume programs broadcast on television and cell phones at an increasingly earlier age. This has generated unimaginable consequences and, Michel Desmurget , in an interview with BCC, in 2022, made the following statement:

What we know for sure is, that even though a child's screen time isn't the only culprit, it does have a significant effect on their IQ. Several studies have shown that when television or video game use increases, IQ and cognitive development decrease (DESMURGET, 2022, sp)

This warning needs to be considered, as the emergence of an entire generation with reduced IQ and cognitive development may lead to few advances in intellectual production in the long term. The entire cultural heritage needs to be interpreted and the existing gaps, due to the lack of knowledge about the psychology of the object, filled through research, in each new generation, so that the results already acquired are not lost and further advances are achieved, through empirical experiments.

Thus, each generation will leave its share of contribution to History. However, this generation has been 'stuffed with useless information' and there is no space left in the cognitive system for learning useful knowledge, necessary for intellectual formation. In the meantime, it is necessary to seek resources so that the intelligence of individuals in the new generations is worked on, so that the ability to innovate, to use inventiveness and creativity, so that sensitivity and talents, intelligence and creative potential are worked from an early age.

THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN INTELLIGENCE

It's not news to anyone that during the first years of life, a child's development takes place through imitation, reproducing everything the adult does and then, little by little, he gains his autonomy, defines the marks of his personality and, Your way of being begins to become well defined. Aware of this situation, parents, guardians, tutors, as well as Early Childhood Education teachers, need to ensure that children find positive situations in every environment they are in to be imitated. Situations of welcome, respect, safety and, above all, empathy, so that they develop as sensitive, supportive and fair people.

When observing childhood, it is also common to notice that, even with all the rights and all the warnings from science, the adult sometimes becomes negligent towards the child. From the moment that in the family, in schools, in public places, you are not guaranteed the right to have contact with leisure, with safety, this could compromise your intellectual, emotional and creative development.

If at home the child spends a lot of time watching television, playing video games, sitting in an armchair, without doing any type of exercise and, if you add to all this a *fast-food diet*, poor in nutrients and rich in low-quality carbohydrates, he will not your psychomotor aspect will be developed in a balanced way, which is the balance between the physical and the cognitive. It will be subject to obesity, hypertension, hypoglycemia, muscle weakness, dry eye syndrome, hearing problems and inadequate posture, which compromises the formation of the skeleton, as well as irritability due to the lack of certain types of vitamins and emotional stress due to contact intense with the virtual world and intolerance due to a certain degree of social isolation. It can generate cognitive impairment due to the overwhelming barrage of information that occupies all your thoughts and leaves you without a moment for leisure. Leisure in this case is that space of time in which the child stops receiving the sounds, colors, movements, special effects that distort the real world through screens and uses his intelligence, talents and creativity to find the solution. to an everyday problem.

Here, it must also be considered that, if at school, the child sits in an inappropriate chair, with his legs dangling, most of the time, paying attention to the teacher's lectures, solving activities that have no meaning for him or that does not challenge you, your ability to concentrate and your interest in learning could be compromised and most of the content taught by the teacher ends up being lost, meaning the much-desired learning does not occur. This could lead her to take even more refuge in the screen, because, due to the colors, the movement, and the desire to solve the challenge proposed there or to see the problem that gave rise to the video game's plot resolved, the film is more favorable to keep her concentrated, as it holds her attention.

The opposite also applies, a child who has his mind occupied with visual stimuli, movements, colors and with the concern of finding a strategy to defeat the game's villain or another situation, will be so overwhelmed that he will have no space left in his space. your thoughts to give way to the school lesson.

So, if she receives it right away, she doesn't need to imagine anything. If what she receives doesn't concern her and doesn't bring her anything new, it won't arouse her interest; Therefore, if the teaching process does not awaken your interest or your inventive and creative capacity, all learning will be compromised. In this case, it is necessary to emphasize that both at school and at home, children receive a range of ready-made information, which does not give them the opportunity to think about the subjects studied and apply them in practice, in their daily lives. day.

In this regard, Jean-Jacques Rousseau (2009) already argued that students should not be given any kind of verbal lesson, letting their own experience teach them and lead them to logical reasoning about things. However, this experience that the philosopher talks about only happens when the child has the possibility of putting theory into practice, through active achievement, and this is only possible when they have the opportunity to observe, think and create based on what is observed. and, above all, to participate in competitions, performances, games, and nursery rhymes. She observes a car and thinks about the possibility of recreating it using pet bottles, liters of oil, pieces of wood and, when observing a baby or adult, she is able to realize that in nature there are forms that can be adapted or children to be dolls, story characters, such as new ears of corn with hair, pumpkins with necks, puppies, cats and rabbits, corn cobs, pieces of wood, among others. All of this is called playing. Using toys or staged or sung games.

Children must have the opportunity to learn through active achievement, creating, inventing, playing, staging, adapting and, above all, imagining possibilities and answers to the problems they face in their daily lives, whether at home or in the classroom. school, because,

when she receives everything ready, she will never know the process of building, discovering and achieving something. As is the case with behavior, the child needs to experience, through games and games, attitudes of respect, partnership, commitment, sharing and, above all, the exercise of empathy.

When involved in activities that require thinking and seeking strategies to solve problems, the child becomes aware of what is happening; However, due to their lack of cognitive maturity to understand the objective world as it is, it is necessary for adults to use symbolism, that is, to use games and pretend play, dressed in costume and wonderful, so that, little by little, this understanding happens.

As most children attend daycare centers from a very early age, it is necessary to think of strategies so that they can make discoveries through observation and touching, not just artificially created objects. It is necessary to think about the inclusion of animals and plants, living beings such as flowers, fruits, leaves, branches and animals with fur, feathers, as well as smooth, rough, small and slightly larger stones, water, clay, sand, wood, small dry twigs; in short, everything that gives them contact with different textures, aromas, flavors, colors, sizes and weights, which awaken different feelings and sensations. Meanwhile, the adult, parents/teachers, gives them their names, shapes and notions of sizes and mass, big/small, rough/smooth/silky, thin/thick, light/heavy, sweet/sour, among others, otherwise, will complete Basic Education without being able to read the world around them adequately, as they have been deprived of the aspect of comparison, which is so necessary for the formation of their autonomy.

It is very common for students to reach Elementary School II and High School, and even Graduation, as if they were affected by a type of pathology of resistance to thinking, both physical and psychological; acting as if thinking hurt a lot and the symptoms are as follows: avoidance of activities that require thinking such as writing and calculating; manifestation of suffering as if being slapped before a text to be read; apathy and verbal self-defense with justifications such as 'I don't know and I can't write, my head hurts, I have no subject to write about, I'm stupid, a teacher', an illness that could be called *Dead Poets Syndrome*. This happens because the practice of reading and writing has always been postponed and neglected by the school, when the teacher works with summaries, offers interpretation scripts as if the texts were ready, finished and does not open up possibilities for a multidisciplinary approach, which would allow a broader and deeper view on the topic read. Therefore, in order not to let this syndrome affect the student, it is necessary to break with bookish teaching practices, which encourage the child to receive the content all ready, finished and sanctified.

The child needs to understand that knowledge is the result of years and years of research, raising hypotheses and experiences, which are motivated by a problem and that the result is the conclusion that the researcher reached, based on theories of others researchers and their own analysis. Throughout this process, the researcher was actively involved, reading different authors, comparing with other similar research, deducing, raising hypotheses, then confirming or refuting them during the process.

In this case, in the family and, especially at school, the child must be made to face problem situations that require them to think of strategies to solve them, and one of the most recommended strategies for reaching the child is play, in which playfulness enters as a methodology and the other is listening to someone tell stories, especially fairy tales.

Within a psychoanalytic view, with regard to existential perplexity regarding the growth process, Bettelheim makes the following observation in relation to fairy tales:

To master the psychological problems of growing up – overcoming narcissistic disappointments, oedipal dilemmas, sibling rivalries, being able to abandon childhood dependencies; to obtain a feeling of individuality and self-worth, and a sense of moral obligation – the child needs to understand what is going on inside their unconscious self. He can achieve this understanding, and with it the ability to deal with things, not by rationally understanding the nature and contents of his unconscious, but by becoming familiar with it through prolonged daydreaming – ruminating, reorganizing and fantasizing about the appropriate elements. of the story in response to pressures from the unconscious. With this, the child adapts the unconscious content to conscious fantasies, which enables him to deal with this content. This is where fairy tales have unparalleled value, as they offer new dimensions to a child's imagination that they could not truly do on their own. Even more important: the form and structure of fairy tales suggest images to the child with which they can structure their daydreams and with them give better direction to life (BETTELHEIM, 1980, p. 16).

Listen to stories in which the protagonists, involved in internal existential dilemmas and with disabilities, manage to find the solution, which can ensnare the child, according to their age. May they bring her light on her own internal dilemmas, through the wonderful, without the objective moral character of the exterior. Just like charades; divinations; crosswords; word search; rhymes; trovas, songs such as *The Lying Cockroach*, *The Crooked House*, *The Funny House*, *The Tin Man*, *Meu Limão Meu Limoeiro*, among others. Folk games such as passing a ring, dead/alive, wheel, hatched egg, burnt whip, blind snake, shuttlecock, marble, and finally, the adult must offer challenges, smooth and sudden movements, pleasant sounds of rhymes, alliteration, images that are pleasing to the eye like works of art, photographs of nature, among others.

It is necessary to rescue, in the midst of this digital world, marked by the encouragement of unbridled consumerism and disposables, the individual's inventiveness, imagination, creativity, talents, intelligence and, above all, guarantee the formation of critical sense and values such as respect and preservation of life, otherwise it will become a manipulable, obedient and uncritical citizen, consuming and discarding indiscriminately and being gradually consumed by an infamous and corrupt system. These people command and control the world with the power of money and what's worse, they give the impression that they are taking care of the less privileged, they offer free schools, with free textbooks, with their content and methodologies ready and finished. While, in fact, the less favored are exploited without pity or mercy through a powerful instrument, which is education, because the way it is offered, coming from top to bottom, and the way in which the professionals there are devalued, it is used to alienate and keep individuals captive in their own ignorance and superstitions.

In this regard, it is worth remembering a passage from the Modern Fable, *If Sharks Were Men*, by the German writer Bertolt Brecht (1890-1956), in the year 1950, of the 20th Century:

It would seem to the little fish that this future would only be guaranteed if they learned obedience. (...) If sharks were men, it would also put an end to the idea that all fish are the same. Some of them would become officials and would be placed above the others. Those slightly larger could even eat the smaller ones. This would be enjoyable for the sharks, as they would more often than not have larger mouthfuls to eat. The bigger fish in positions would take care of internal order among the fish, becoming teachers, officials, police officers, cage builders, etc. In short, if sharks were men, there would be a civilization in the sea (BRECHT, 2015, sp).

And here, one might say, in what civilization, a few control and the majority obey without question?

As soon as those responsible for forming opinions, teachers, do not begin to question the contents, methodologies, their working conditions, their devaluation as professionals and begin to look at everything with a critical view, they will no longer accept being manipulation instrument and are already beginning to work towards contributing to the student's comprehensive education. Not the comprehensive training that is preached in today's booklets, in public schools, in which the speech is read and the same methodological practices are maintained in which teachers transmit and students receive the content, repeating Paulo Freire's famous banking education.

It is necessary to analyze events and technological advances and think of a way to use them as instruments in favor of pedagogy. The competition between teaching methodologies and technology has generated many setbacks and disagreements, in which the school, the

teacher and, especially the students, are at a disadvantage. The sounds, the movement, the colors, the diversity of images, the rhythm, a whole sum of appealing elements that capture the attention of the viewer/consumer. Various subjects and themes covered in videos, slides, stories, films, reels, social networks with such a great seductive power that the reader/viewer often consumes unconsciously and without criteria a range of useless and disjointed information that fills their head; but which do not generate significant and important knowledge for the intellectual development of that individual.

If before the use of the computer, the system guaranteed that Education would be used to de(form) the new generations, so that they would remain in the same situation, without creativity, without talents, without inventiveness, that is, poor in the condition of poor, average as a secondary student, the situation may become more complicated, with the insertion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in schools and teaching processes. In this context, so that the school team does not lose focus and, above all, rethinks about the materials that come into their hands, about their methodologies, about their notion, vision and the concept they have of children and the need to offer themselves moments for 'creative leisure', that is, the moment in which the child has contact with playing. Playing with words, in stories, nursery rhymes, trovas, tongue twisters, staged songs. Playing with the whole body, hopscotch, tag, marbles, burnt whip, goro egg and many other games and, above all, having pleasurable contact with children's literature.

In the meantime, the team needs to rethink its pedagogical practice, considering some questions. Does the school team know what it is like to be a child and how they learn? Sometimes it is believed not, since the teacher has spent a lot of time being manipulated by the authoritarian system, which still believes that if he follows the manuals and textbooks, he is teaching reading, writing and calculation of the form adequate, but research already shows that this is not enough for learning to occur, and critical training to boot. Here, it is worth highlighting the words of Ezequiel Theodoro da Silva, in which he states that, "attributing responsibilities for political decisions and actions to the government, many educators remain kneeling and with their heads down, hoping that the results coming from above are favorable to educational issues and cultural aspects of a people." (SILVA, 1991, p. 11). And, further on, the same author reinforces the warning: "the promotion of student readers becomes weaker, when to-order book merchants insist on deceiving teachers with textbooks of dubious quality and, in this way, deceiving students with textbooks" (Idem, 1991, p. 15).

Given the above, another question arises: does the team know how the external world and children's experiences can be used by the school? It is also believed that the team does not know and is not interested in knowing nor does it want to learn; therefore, teachers were trained

in such a way that they continue to believe that adults are the owners of the truth and textbooks and curricular proposals need to be followed, without being questioned. In this regard, Perrotti (1986) and Cunha (1997) make the following observation: “The domination of the childish spirit intended by the commodity-discourse is clear, it serves the dominant order, whatever its nature. In the case of Brazilians, it serves to perpetuate the state of dependence in which we live, in addition to being a consequence of the state” (PERROTTI *apud* CUNHA, 1997, p. 78).

Does the team know what notions children have about themselves at each age and the peculiarities of each one? In this case, the situation gets even worse, as society and public policies determine what the child needs to know, often, in each grade, without considering age, particularities and interest and, above all, support. of content in Science and Literature and this does not guarantee learning, as knowledge from different areas is plastered in books as teaching content. In this sense, Cunha (1997) makes the following observation: “One of the causes of students' lack of interest is this conditioning, this tranquility with which we go, year after year, bringing children the same books, the same stories, always assuming the same activities. for equal students” (CUNHA, 1997, p. 18).

How does the child feel about the positive and negative stimuli he receives? Here, the teacher can be induced to believe that he should not demand from his students so as not to generate frustration; In this case, he may be at the mercy of *trying to please* all the time, without worrying that the child needs to face diversity, to self-understand, self-regulate, self-control in the face of frustrations and challenges and that, ends up getting lost in the face of the countless demands to which the teacher is subjected in his practice. In the opinion of Silva (1991, p. 37) “the Brazilian school is forgotten, abandoned. The powerful ideological injections that injected bureaucracy, authoritarianism and domination into teachers during the dictatorial period maintain their effects to this day”.

In this case, in the daily routine of schools, the teacher teaches, without considering the prior knowledge and interests of his students. And yet, if there is another question, what are the impacts on a child's life, when they do not have the right to daydreams and the opportunity to understand and overcome them at each stage of their life? Offering the real, written in figurative language, through which the marvelous and enchantment of Literature and the denotative language of Science are created, and not of didactic content, all values and useful things can be explored in the classroom through play. What can happen to the child from the moment of frustration regarding screen consumption and the moment of creative leisure?

As the individual goes through different times and phases of cognitive development, he, like a sponge, absorbs everything that goes on around him and especially contact with screens

and, in most cases, without the appropriate filter. This, often, already in adolescence, he shows a marked lack of interest in school content, family guidance and this can manifest itself through tiredness, a lack of energy with no apparent explanation. Sometimes it's not a lack of interest in learning; in fact, it is the uninteresting content, transmitted mechanically that does not attract you in the same way as that displayed on screens; Thus, he consumes everything at the same time and does not have space in his brain to learn the essentials.

There is a popular saying that says that *the occasion makes the thief*. Given this mass supply of disconnected and intense information, when will children have the opportunity to use their intelligence and creativity to study the solution to problems that arise in their daily lives? At these times in the process of technological development and the unbridled supply of information and auditory and visual appeals, it is necessary to learn to use strategies to 'steal' the time that screens take away from individuals, so that they learn to create, to invent and to lift hypotheses and search for objective answers. Here, one of the most appropriate strategies is the games offered in early childhood, in families and schools. It is necessary to view playfulness not as something of minor importance, which only generates pleasure; rather, as a fundamental teaching methodology for all human formation, body expression and language, feelings such as joys and frustrations and the construction of logical thinking.

According to the nature of playing, it is possible that some professionals see this process as playful; however, play is a scientific research methodology that requires a multidisciplinary team made up of a psychiatrist, psychologist, educational psychologist and teacher to use it in controlled experiments. Thus, playing here can be seen as an active methodology.

For Silva, Biegging and Busarello (2017),

These methodologies use problematization as a goal to motivate the learner to develop reflections on ideas based on the problem presented, relating their history and starting to give new meaning to their discoveries to apply them in practice. Faced with problematization, the learner reflects on the information, producing knowledge with the aim of resolving doubts and concerns regarding problems, thus promoting their own development through the construction and reconstruction of knowledge (SILVA, BIEGING and BUSARELLO 2027, p. 14).

Through play, it is possible to give new meaning to information, come across problem situations and challenges, form values such as mutual respect, develop attention, concentration, language, body expression, social interaction, motor coordination, balance, perception and, above all, the different verbal and non-verbal languages.

To do this, it is necessary to resort not only to current games, but also to folk games and toys such as: ring pass, hide and seek, ring pass, jump rope, tug of war, hopscotch, blind goat,

cat-mia, whip. burnt, chocolate egg, hot potato, musical chairs, marbles, spinning top, kites, figurines, slingshot, language games (talks, rhymes, tongue twisters), charades, What is it? What is it? Among others.

In this sense, Costa makes the following statement:

The sung game contributes to the development of oral expression, hearing, rhythm, balance, motor coordination, physical exercise, among other important benefits. The sung game allows everyone to experience childhood. Therefore, school life in the early childhood education phase means experiencing remarkable moments that in other times were lived in the family context, today forgotten by the day-to-day rush of the parents or guardians of the child (COSTA, 2022, p. 93).

This category includes the nursery rhymes, The Rich and the Poor, where is Margarida, A Linda Rosa Juvenil, falls into the well, Job's slaves, melon capelinha, crab is not a fish, I went to the market, live fish, ciranda cirandinha, three, three “will pass” Three, three will pass, I went to Tororó, the canoe capsized, Terezinha de Jesus, Father Francisco entered the circle, among others. The sung games are a mixture of bodily and cultural expression. A mix of musicality, dance, drama, mime and games, experienced by generations for hundreds of years and which need to be rescued as a way of alleviating the impacts of excessive use of screens in children's lives. Because, games and toys have behind them a mysterious and magnificent symbolism, a wonderful make-believe and enchanted world capable of reaching and entangling the child's soul in a pleasurable and meaningful way.

Here, you can add the game of listening to stories. In this case, the storyteller needs to take into account the age of his listener. Thus, as the cognitive is linked to the ability to learn, learning to learn, learning to do, learning to be, using the knowledge and information provided by reading different texts. To meet these aspects, it is necessary to establish a link between the cognitive and the affective, so that there is reader motivation. In this regard, the analysis of thought and Schliebe -Lippert and Beinlich cited by Bamberger (2000) is extremely relevant, regarding the classification of readers with regard to their interest in reading:

a) “Age of picture books and children’s verses (2 to 5 or 6 years old). Beinlich characterizes it as “Egocentric, integral-personal initial phase.” The child makes little distinction between the inner and outer world. (...) picture books help when they present simple objects, alone, taken from the environment in which the child lives. (...) He likes nursery rhymes because of the rhythm, the vigorous plastic force of the ideas, the rhythm of the game with words and their sounds.

b) Age of fairy tales (from 5 to 8 or 9 years old). Characterized by Beinlich as the reading age of magical realism. Sustaining development in fantasy. They

prefer characters and stories from a distant world of wonders. The pleasure he finds in rhythm and verse and the love of poetry remain the same.

c) Age of “environmental stories” or “factual” reading (9 to 12 years old). Characterized by Beinlich as “Construction of a practical, realistic, rationally ordered facade, in front of a pseudo-realistically masked magical-adventurous backdrop . The child begins to orient himself in the concrete, objective world. (...) dry descriptions should not be offered, but rather as stories, as living events. The desire for the adventurous begins to emerge.

d) Age of adventure stories: realism or the “non-psychological reading phase oriented towards sensationalism” (from 12 to 14 or 15). Little by little, they become aware of their own personality; it loosens or undoes previous links (the second age of independence and challenge) (...) the formation of readers can be awakened through the plot, the events, the sensationalism, on the part of the boys. As for girls, it often comes to the fore as a reading interest as well as cheap sensationalism and self-adulation . General interests in adventure books, sensational novels, travel books, ordinary stories and cheap sentimentality.

e) The years of maturity or the “development of the aesthetic-literary sphere of reading” (from 14 to 17 years old). Development of one's own inner world of critical egocentrism, development of a life plan, development of various value scales. They value the plot, form and content in reading material. Interest in the outer world is replaced or supplemented by participation in the inner world and the world of values. Reading interests: adventure with more intellectual content, travel books, historical novels, biographies, love stories, current affairs, engaging literature, factual material that is often related to vocational preferences (BAMBERGER, 2000, p. 59).

This is because, according to Charmeux (1994),

Even though there are other forms of access to cultural heritage, thanks to audiovisual techniques, reading continues to be the main tool for personal enrichment, due to its manageability and the constantly available presence of the objects in which it is present, an object of tasting and incomparable pleasure. (Idem, p. 14)

Even though we agree with this author, that the contact with reading, in the book, its texture, smell generates an incomparable pleasure, the competition with the cell phone, nowadays becomes dishonest, due to the fact that the majority of individuals have access to the internet. Internet, through it, which is also an easy-to-use object, which offers a lot of information about politics, police, science, games, among others, due to the lack of reader training, makes the individual, especially younger people, access websites of entertainment and games so that even large online libraries are at risk of closing due to little access. In this context, more than ever, once again, books are forgotten in physical libraries. In previous decades, students did not have access to libraries, they sat and received their portion of daily/school content. Now, with parents, coming from the least favored classes, who (de)graduated from public schools, who did not learn to enjoy reading, who did not learn how pleasurable it is to

play and listen to stories, they left their children without meaningful contact with the book and, therefore, with the delight that the act of reading brings to the reader.

In a literate society, learning to read and understand is fundamental to achieving professional success, freedom and citizen autonomy. Otherwise, he will become a consumer without critical sense, who is also consumed by the 'facilities' that modern life offers, without being aware of what is happening to him. So, playing listening to stories is the basis for children to learn to immerse themselves in this literate world and discover themselves as a person endowed with talents, intelligence and creativity that they will use throughout their lives, in order to survive and conquer 'their place in the Sun'. amidst the alienated and unrestrained consumer mass.

That said, the question arises: How long will the education system provide everything ready and finished for the student? It is known that each scientific discovery takes decades to reach a result; But the student doesn't know that. He receives scientific content devoid of science, with a pedagogical look, with the excuse of making it easier to be understood by the student and evaluated by the teacher and, what is more complicated, before he has the intellectual development to receive the scientific content. And to further complicate the condition of an apprentice reader, the school requires linear reading and demands understanding without being prepared. In this regard, Charmeux (1994, p. 52) warns of the fact that, "by requiring children to read in a linear way in order to immediately understand from this linearity, the school leaves them incapable of developing strategies for constructing sense".

Here, we can add the provision of prose texts for the practice of oral reading, without considering the child's ability to move their eyes. Often, the child is unable to follow the very long line with their eyes and verbalize what they have read; thus, he runs over the words and the teacher/pedagogue considers him as if he still doesn't know how to read, when in fact, the student is able, through silent reading, to read the text completely and establish meaning. When practicing oral reading, the ideal is to make poetic texts available so that the eyes can follow the entire length of the line and verbalize the text.

In the continuation, the author makes an even greater warning: "numerous observations allow us to affirm that the fear of books, 'of written things', the terror and even the repulsion aroused by libraries and even bookstores, are at the origin of a good part of reading failures" (CHARMEUX 1994, p. 75). This failure happens when the student stutters in oral reading and the teacher leaves him to recover or fails.

At school, most of the time, teaching reading is a real fallacy, as they make it as difficult as possible for the student not to learn to enjoy reading, from offering textbooks with

pedagogical texts devoid of science, with *literary texts* devoid of charm and shine. The school that fulfills the role of social controller, the child enters with an adventurous and curious spirit and leaves starved and unwilling to learn. Does anyone have an explanation for this situation? Very easy, poor school, for poor students to remain in poor condition, as it was, is and always will be in the history of this country. Every now and then, one of them escapes and goes to a university to study for a degree, earning master's and doctoral degrees that are predestined for the richest social classes. Why would it be?

When analyzing the life story of this student, who broke the vicious cycle of social class, the teacher will discover that in addition to the content received in the classroom, that student had a history of reading and research, even if it was books found by his parents who work as recycling collectors. Reading, songs and pretend play open up the world of the child's imagination and inventiveness. It's sad for teachers to come across students in the 9th year of elementary school who don't know how to write anything imaginary and creative, they only know how to look for ready-made answers in the texts [*sometimes, even !*]. And this type of activity doesn't require much thinking, just mechanically and giving answers.

It is necessary to consider that the child who plays listening to stories develops into an individual with a holistic and critical view of the world. Play helps to form values such as tolerance, resilience, respect and learn to invent and overcome the frustrations of losses and many other behaviors and attitudes that strengthen good character and altruistic personality.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

When considering play as an active methodology, the adult ensures that the child is significantly involved in the proposed activities. In addition to working with everyday content that is meaningful to the child, sung games, nursery rhymes, games, games and folk toys bring them attitudinal and behavioral training.

It is necessary to remember that the Human Being only acquires an objective notion about life when he becomes an adult, before that he sees the world through the eyes of the marvelous and naive. In order for the child to reach adulthood with the skills and abilities to survive in society as a citizen aware of their rights and duties, the family and educators must give the child the opportunity to play, invent, create and solve problem situations, using your intelligence, your talents and creativity.

REFERENCES

BETTELHEIM, Bruno. *The psychoanalysis of fairy tales* . Paz e Terra Publisher. Rio de Janeiro, 1980.

BRECHT, Bertold. *If sharks were men* . Available: <https://revistaforum.com.br/cultura/2015/2/25/se-os-tubares-fossem-homens-por-bertold-brecht-154.html> . Accessed Jan 21 2014.

CHARMEUX, Eveline. *Learning to read: overcoming failure*. São Paulo: Editor Cortez, 1994.

COSTA, Eroni Ferreira da. In: SILVEIRA, Jader Luís da (Org.). *Education in Action : Theories and Practices*. Ant: Editora Ducere , 2022.

CUNHA, Maria Antonieta Antunes. *Children's Literature: Theory and Practice*. Editora Ática AS. São Paulo, 1997.

DESMURGET Michel. '*Digital generation*' : Why , for the first time, children have a lower IQ than their parents. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/portuguese/geral-54736513> . 10/30/2020. Accessed June 13, 2023. By Irene Hernández Velasco – Special for BBC News Mundo.

NERY JÚNIOR, Nelson; NERY, Rosa Maria de Andrade. Art. 71 of the Child and Adolescent Statute - Law 8069/90. Available <https://www.jusbrasil.com.br/doutrina/leis-civis-comentadas-e-anotadas/1153074667> . Accessed: July 11, 2023.

CUNHA, Maria Antonieta Antunes. *Children's Literature : Theory and Practice*. São Paulo: Editora Ática, 1997.

BAMBERGUER, Richard. *How to motivate reading habits* . São Paulo: Ática, 2000

ROUSSEAU Jean-Jacques. *Emílio or education*. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2009.

SILVA, Andreza Regina Lopes da; BIEGING, Patrícia; BUSARELLO, Raul Inácio (Eds .). *Active methodology in education* . São Paulo: Pimenta Cultural, 2017.

SILVA, Ezequiel Theodoro da. *With Open Eyes : Reflections on the development of reading in Brazil*. São Paulo: Editora Ática, 1991.